

CEREBRAL VENOUS SINUS THROMBOSIS IN NEWBORNS**Rahimova N.J.,***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Scientific Research Institute named after K.Farajova Baku, Azerbaijan, AZ 370165, Basti Baqirova 17;
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Venous thrombosis is a pathological condition in which, as a result of the formation of an intravascular thrombus, the blood flow in the tissues is abruptly interrupted or limited. A number of studies have shown that in adults, activation of the blood coagulation system against the background of a cytokine storm due to SARS-CoV-2 led to ischemic stroke and intracranial hemorrhage. An analysis of numerous studies in children with systemic inflammatory syndrome revealed an unexpectedly high incidence of ischemic and hemorrhagic cerebrovascular complications in them. Our article describes the clinical picture of parenchymal hemorrhage, as well as thrombosis of the cerebral venous sinuses in a newborn, which developed as a result of a multisystem inflammatory syndrome associated with SARS-Cov2.

Keywords: newborn, multisystem inflammatory syndrome, cerebral venous sinus thrombosis.

Introduction. Thrombosis of cerebral (brain) veins and venous sinuses is a rare disease that occurs as a result of the formation of a blood clot in the venous sinuses of the brain, has a severe clinical course and results in a number of complications [1,2].

Unlike arterial thrombosis, thrombosis of cerebral veins and venous sinuses is more common in young people and children and accounts for less than 1% of all stroke cases. In newborns, the incidence varies between 1-12/100,000 [3,4]. Recent results from the International Pediatric Stroke Study show that more than half of all cerebral sino-venous thromboses diagnosed in childhood occur in the neonatal period, and are more common in boys than in girls.

Violation of the body's hemostasis system can be cited as the main reason for the development of thrombosis in cerebral veins and venous sinuses. Due to a number of different infectious and non-infectious causes, hemostasis system disorders can develop, so during the current pandemic, it is often found in patients with COVID-19 [7]. It should be noted that at the end of April 2020, SARS-CoV-2 among children in many countries It has been reported that a multisystem inflammatory syndrome-MIS-C (Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children) developed due to infection and had a severe course [8]. It has been seen that this clinical picture develops after 4-6 weeks, mainly in children, when they are infected with COVID-19, and is accompanied by a violation of the function of many organs, as well as hemostasis, including neurological complications [9]. A review of multiple studies in children with MIS-C found ischemic and hemorrhagic cerebrovascular complications, as well as an unexpectedly high rate (34%) of neurological symptoms [10,11,12].

In our article, the clinical picture of parenchymatous hemorrhage, and cerebral venous sinus thrombosis

in a newborn developing multisystem inflammatory syndrome related to SARS-Cov2 is described.

Material. Patient ZM (medical card - 006253/764209), a 15-day-old girl, was admitted to our clinic from home in a serious condition. It is known from the anamnesis that the child was born in one of the small clinics, I pregnancy, I delivery. He was discharged home on the third day of his life. During the current pregnancy, the mother was infected with SARS-CoV-2 infection at 37 weeks of pregnancy. Currently, he has been ill for 2 days and has a high fever.

His condition was very serious when he entered. Continual convulsions were observed by the CNS, the neck muscles are rigid, the patient is in a compulsive state, convulses, reflexes are absent, and his gaze is fixed on one point. The leather covers are worn and pale grayish in color. Respiration is shallow, and tachypnea is noted. SpO2 values are normally. Heart tones are deafened, and pulse is arrhythmic. His belly is soft. Physiological acts were not observed during the examination. Considering the patient's condition, he was admitted to the intensive care unit for examination and treatment.

The patient was immediately assisted: anticonvulsant measures were taken, he was placed in a bathtub, monitoring with nasal O2 support was started, the patient was monitored by a monitor, peripheral vascular access was opened, NQZ was inserted, and the bladder was catheterized. USM of the brain was immediately performed - GRADE III bleeding was observed, brain MRI was advised. A SARS Cov-2 swab was taken from the child, the result was negative. Full parenteral nutrition, anticonvulsant treatment and empiric antibacterial therapy were started, platelet mass was transferred due to low platelets, clexan was added to the prescription according to the hematologist's decision.

Despite intensive therapy, no positive dynamics were noted in the patient's condition, cardiac arrest was noted on the 7th day of treatment, bradycardia continued despite resuscitation measures, and the patient died.

Laboratory tests carried out: blood group: AB (IV) Rh negative (-).

Hemogram: HGB-10.1 g/dl, HCT-28.4, RBC-2.8*10⁶, RDW-16.4, MCHC-35.5, MCH -35.9, MCV -101, WBC - 10.3, N - 54.1%, lymph-33.9 %, E-0.922 %, M-8.86 %, B - 0.224, PLT-37.9, PDW -18.3, PCT -0.021, MPV -5.52

Coagulogram: prothrombin time+ in R-1.23, prothrombin activation-68.4, prothrombin time-16.2, active partial thromboplastin time-34, D - Dimer-11564 ng/ml, Vitamin B12-486, Ferritin-850.7, LDH-580,

Blood gases: PH-7.320, pCO₂-44.5, pO₂-79.0, HCO₃-21.6, ABE-3.3, Lac-1.7, SpO₂-96.7 %

Biochemical examination of blood: sugar-136 mg/dl, potassium-3.4 mmol/l, sodium-141 mmol/l, calcium-8.5 mmol/l, magnesium-1.75 mmol/l, total protein (blood)-5.09 G/l, albumin-3.2 g/l, total bilirubin-1.74 mkmol/l, creatinine - 0.4 mkmol/l, residual nitrogen (BUN)-4V, AST-109v, alt-72V, procalcitonin-0.13 V, CRZ-1.73 mg/mL, TSH-5.1881 V.

SARS-CoV-2 (IgM) - 0.07, SARS-CoV-2 (IgG)-456.7

Instrumental examinations carried out: Doppler+Color echocardiography: functional open botal flow, IAS aneurysm /secundum ASD.

Chest X-ray (taken on a portative apparatus in an anterior-flat projection): the chest is normosthenic, the intercostal areas and their orientation have not changed. Destructive and traumatic changes in visible bones are not noted. The nasogastral probe is noted. Low-intensity mesh shading of the lung areas is noted on both sides. Enlargement of the lymph nodes around the walls and bronchi is not noted. The diaphragm and sinuses are free.

Heart-condition, shape and boundaries are within the norm The large vessels - the aorta and arterial pulmonalis arcs-unchanged.

Ultrasound of internal organs: the contour of the liver is smooth, its size, parenchyma exogenicity, struk-tour correspond to age. Focal pathology, which takes place in the liver, is not traced. The hepatic and portal venous system did not change, the intra-and extra-hepatic bile ducts did not expand. The size and walliness of the gallbladder corresponds to the norm, no noticeable stones or derivatives are found in it, the total bile flow has not expanded.

Ultrasound of internal organs: the contour of the liver is smooth, its size, parenchyma exogenicity, structure related to age. Focal pathology, which takes place in the liver, is not traced. The hepatic and portal venous system did not change, the intra-and extra-hepatic bile

ducts did not expand. The size and walliness of the gallbladder related to the norm, no noticeable stones or derivatives are found in it, the total bile flow has not expanded.

The dimensions of the spleen related to age, the exostructure of its parenchyma is homogeneous. The thickness ,exogenicity and structure of the pancreas are normal.

The localization, contour and demension of the kidneys related to age. The thickness of the parenchyma is within the norm, the EXO-structure is homogeneous. Noticeable stone or neoplasm are not traced. Pelvicalyceal system did not expand in both kidneys. Pathology in the adrenal glands is not noted. The urinary bladder wall thickness is normal, no stones or neoplasm are detected in it.

Intraabdominal mass, free fluid not traced.

Neurosonography: Subarachnoidal areas and interhemispheric distance are the norm, while their composition is heterogeneous. In the coronal cut, subependymal hemorrhage of a high degree of exogenous structure. Bleeding filling are noted in the frontal horns, trunk and occipital horns of the lateral ventricles. Hemorrhage of larger sizes on the left in the caudothalamic area produces a dislocation of ~ 1 cm from the midline to the right. Choroid plexus is not clearly differentiated against the background of hemorrhage.

A clot is noted in the subarachnoid area in the posterior fossa, in the cysterna magna and in the IV ventricle. Color Doppler ultrasound shows turbulent flow in the pericallosal artery.

Result: cerebral hemorrhage Grade III.

Head brain MRT: semi-acute period thrombosis of venous sinuses and related, hemorrhagic venous infarction in basal ganglia, thalamus, intraventricular hemorrhage and territorial ischemic stroke areas in both cerebral hemispheric parenchyma are in favor.

Electroenceologram recorded: iso electric line is traced.

Based on the conducted clinical-laboratory-instrumental examinations, the patient was given the following diagnosis: Diffuse brain hemorrhage Grade III. Thrombosis of venous sinuses (subacute period). Hemorrhagic venous infarction in the thalamus. Intraventricular hemorrhage. Territorial ischemic stroke in the parenchyma of the cerebral hemispheres.

Treatment: Antibacterial, anticonvulsant, anticoagulant, symptomatic .

Conclusion: Thus, our clinical observation shows that as a result of SARS-CoV-2 infection, the multisystem inflammatory syndrome can develop in newborns, which can lead to death by causing intracerebral hemorrhages and ischemic stroke in babies. In this regard, newborns born to mothers infected with SARS-CoV-2 should be constantly monitored for the development of multisystem inflammatory syndrome.

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